

Designing Web Based Constructivist Learning Environments

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Abstract: A group of 18 university teachers designing and constructing a Constructivist Learning Environment (CLE) was interviewed and monitored in order to find and test optimal design of web based CLEs. The information functions of the CLE were supported by web based technology and the social / collaborative functions were designed using “face to face” interaction. The learning environment was designed for use by a group of 180 first year students with no experience in using CLEs. The results show that supporting the information functions of a CLE with web based technology can be very useful for case oriented education. It also supplied good support for efficient instructional design by a group of teachers. In addition it resulted in a shift of teachers behavior towards facilitating active learning.

Introduction

The last decade of the previous century has brought two developments with important consequences for design of instruction (Tam, 2000). The first development is the changing perception of what learning is about. Learning has long been seen as the result of knowledge transfer from teachers or knowledge transmission from information sources. Now the constructivist conception of learning has gained recognition, stressing the idea that knowledge is individually constructed by learners based on their interpretations of experiences in the world. Instructional design should thus focus on creating constructivist learning environments (CLEs) that engage learners in meaning making and knowledge construction (Jonassen, 1998). The second development is the use of information technology enabling new ways of exploring information, social interaction and constructing information sources. These two developments combine well as virtual experiences and web based sharing of results and viewpoints adds possibilities to individually construct knowledge (Rice & Wilson, 1999).

According to Jonassen (1998) CLEs should supply:

- questions / cases / problems / projects
- related cases
- information resources
- cognitive (knowledge-construction) tools
- conservation and collaboration Tools
- social / contextual support

The first four functions are dealing with information (construction) and they can be supported by web based technology. The last two functions are aimed at social interaction, and the information technology support of them is well described in the literature covering Computer Supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL). CSCL is often the main focus for the introduction of information technology in education. However it is still not very clear what advantage CSCL has compared to “face to face” implementations of collaborative learning if there is no need to bridge time or location differences. In general the first four functions mentioned above might benefit from web based technology regardless of the need to bridge time and location differences.

Purpose

The purpose of the research reported in this paper was to find and test optimal design strategies for CLEs using web technology support for the information (construction) functions.

Methods

In 1999 Wageningen University (in the Netherlands) had planned a major change in its study programmes starting with the courses for the new students arriving in September 2000. As a result of this the educational institute for environmental sciences (EIES) had to design a new introduction course for environmental science students. The institute wanted the introduction course to be case oriented with active participation of students. In addition the course had to be multidisciplinary by using input of university teachers from 14 different department groups. Stoas assisted the EIES in this task by formulating a project aimed at interactive group design using Web technology. The EIES scheduled group design sessions from April till September 2000. The meetings were at irregular intervals about two times each month. The group of 18 designing teachers was formed between March and July with most teachers participating by June. The teachers were all new to ICT supported case oriented learning, and had not been working together in this group before. The course had to be ready for use in September. It would be used by 180 first year students with no experience in ICT supported case oriented learning.

The teachers were interviewed at the beginning of the design process and after the students had finished their tasks at the end of the course. The meetings of the teachers were monitored during the design, construction and utilization phases and student satisfaction was monitored at the end using a web based questionnaire.

Results and discussion

The design phase

At the beginning of the design process the teachers had no clear idea on how to proceed and they had doubts about the available resources for the design, construction and utilization phases. However in general they showed to be prepared to “jump in the dark” and were willing to discuss instructional design based on principles they were not familiar with. In the first meetings the teachers agreed on an approach using cases build on problem specifications and information resources. In addition it was decided that the social interaction and collaborative work needed during the course would be done in group gatherings (18 groups of 10 students) of 4 hours during 7 weeks. There was a clear consensus to use a face to face approach for these meetings as that was considered essential for new students. The student groups would have to elaborate on the problems they could specify using the course cases presented on the web. The construction of group work presentations would be facilitated using general presentation software (Microsoft Power Point) and a student software training was included in the course. The students would be introduced to the course on a plenary introduction session on the first day.

By the beginning of June the teachers had thus made major decisions on all the functions of a CLE mentioned in the introduction and gathered some case material as well. Yet most group members had problems creating course content as a clear framework for the case information was missing. At that point Stoas made a design for the web based information functions, incorporating all the work the group had done so far. A simple design using web pages was selected as there was no need for student tracking or a secluded learning environment.

The construction phase

The design for the web based functions was approved and build on the web within one week. In the following weeks group discussions were based on the structure and examples on the web. Most teachers were able to provide substantial input as they had just attended a joined web page construction course (using Microsoft FrontPage). In addition to the case content, the group constructed a joint environmental science glossary. That was an important step as the 14 department involved had not confronted the students with consistency in definitions in the past. Course information functions like a work schedule, teacher contact data and a search function were added as well. Also a library containing pictures with environmental science related explanations was constructed. These pictures were described using an international standard for educational metadata (ARIADNE, 1999). This enables the collection to be part of a University wide or international database.

The course execution and evaluation phase

The course started on the 4th of September, by that time all web based information functions were completed. The design for the group work was almost finished (some parts for the last course weeks were added later) and the 18 group work rooms were made available that day. The course lasted 7 weeks and the students used the web based information functions to formulate and solve their case questions. The students assigned each other tasks and worked alone and in small groups to accomplish them. Each group room was equipped with 1-5 computers. Student couldn't work efficiently in the few rooms with only one or two computers. The students presented their work half way and at the end. The teachers were pleasantly surprised by the quality of these presentations. A web based questionnaire on the quality of the course was introduced in the last week. The response to this questionnaire was 60% (108 out of 180). In general the course scored well with exception of the first part which had suffered from the time stress due to the late start of the design process. The teachers were all pleased with this type of education and they had liked their new role.

Conclusions

Facilitating effective group interaction is essential for designing web based CLEs as usually all the CLE facilities needed can't be constructed by one person. A group design process requires frequent work meetings. In the first meetings the teachers can help each other in understanding new learning approaches. It is important that those discussions results in joint decisions about the instructional design. In addition the group should decide on web design standards to be used. Web based functions can be designed as soon as major decision on instructional design are taken. The construction of these functions is needed as a trigger to enable the entire design to be constructed by the group

Supporting the information (construction) functions with web based technology can result in a shift of teachers behavior towards facilitating active learning. In addition it can create a good basis for intensive group work.

Constructing cases for CLEs is time consuming and web based support doesn't change that much. Web based cases are an excellent use of information technology for education, however complicated case material requires combination with the social functions of CLEs in order to be effectively utilized.

The group work was done in large groups of 10 students. In general the groups reached good results but a design with more variation in group size as described by Heath et al. (1999) might be more efficient.

The CLE made the students cooperate nicely and it made the teachers cooperate in a way they had never done before.

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URL of university involved:
Wageningen University:

<https://www.wur.nl/en.htm>

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